

ID	Description	Status	Priority
US01	As a User, I want to register myself, so that I can create and manage workspaces with my team members.	Implemented	Must Have
US02	As a User, I want to log in to the website, so that I can access my personal account and preferences.	Implemented	Must Have
US03	As a User, I want to delete my account, so that I can protect my privacy and stop using the service.	Implemented	Must Have
US04	As a User, I want to create a workspace, so that I can organize my projects and manage workspace members.	Implemented	Must Have
US05	As a Workspace Admin, I want to invite users to a workspace, so that we can work in the same environment.	Implemented	Must Have
US06	As a Workspace Admin, I want to list workspace members, so that I can manage them.	Implemented	Must Have
US07	As a Workspace Admin, I want to control their workspace roles, so that I can manage their permissions in my workspace.	Implemented	Must Have
US08	As a Workspace Admin, I want to remove members from my workspace, so that I can manage the access to my workspace.	Implemented	Must Have
US09	As a Workspace Admin, I want to edit my workspace information, so that I can keep it updated and relevant.	In Analysis	Must Have
US10	As a Workspace Admin, I want to delete my workspace, so that I can remove it from the system if I no longer need it.	In Analysis	Must Have
US11	As a Workspace Member, I want to create projects, so that I can manage and organize my projects.	In Analysis	Must Have
US12	As a Workspace Member, I want to list my projects, so that I can navigate through my different projects.	In Analysis	Must Have
US13	As a Project Admin, I want to edit my project, so that I can keep it updated and relevant.	In Analysis	Must Have
US14	As a Project Admin, I want to delete my project, so that I can remove it from the system if I no longer need it.	In Analysis	Must Have
US15	As a Project Member, I want to import/export from/to Excel format, so that I can manipulate project data.	Implemented	Should Have

US16	As a Project Member, I want to create a project charter, so that I can establish the purpose and goals of the project. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US17	As a Project Member, I want to update the project charter, so that I can keep the project up-to-date as review are made.(integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US18	As a Project Member, I want to create a business case, so that I can register the business needs.(integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US19	As a Project Member , I want to update the business case, so that I can keep the document up-to-date as changes are required. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US20	As a Project Member, I want to create the benefits management plan, so that I can define how benefits will be managed. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US21	As a Project Member, I want to update the benefits management plan, so that I keep it up-to-date as changes are made. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US22	As a Project Member, I want to create constraints and assumptions of my project, so that I can organize potential risks or issues.	Implemented	Must Have
US23	As a Project Member, I want to list the assumption log items, so that I can manage them.	Implemented	Must Have
US24	As a Project Member, I want to update assumption log items, so that I can keep the items up-to-date.	Implemented	Must Have
US25	As a Project Member, I want to delete assumption log items, so that I can remove useless items.	Implemented	Must Have
US26	As a Project Member, I want to create the project management plan, so that I can detail how the project execution will work.	Implemented	Must Have
US27	As a Project Member, I want to update the project management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date as changes are required.	Implemented	Must Have
US28	As a Project Member, I want to create project performance and monitoring reports items, so that I can organize the project progress.	Implemented	Must Have
US29	As a Project Member, I want to list project performance and monitoring report items, so that I can manage them.	Implemented	Must Have

US30	As a Project Member, I want to update project performance and monitoring report items, so that I can keep the progress up-to-date.	Implemented	Must Have
US31	As a Project Member, I want to delete project performance and monitoring items, so that I can remove unnecessary data.	Implemented	Must Have
US32	As a Project Member, I want to create deliverable status items, so that I can organize the project deliveries.	Implemented	Must Have
US33	As a Project Member, I want to list deliverable status items, so that I can manage them.	Implemented	Must Have
US34	As a Project Member, I want to update deliverable status items, so that I can keep the items up-to-date.	Implemented	Must Have
US35	As a Project Member, I want to delete deliverable status items, so that I can remove unnecessary data.	Implemented	Must Have
US36	As a Project Member, I want to create work performance items, so that I can organize the team performance. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US37	As a Project Member, I want to list work performance items, so that I can manage them. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US38	As a Project Member, I want to update work performance items, so that I can keep the team progress up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US39	As a Project Member, I want to delete project performance and monitoring items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US40	As a Project Member, I want to create issue log items, so that I can organize the project issues. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US41	As a Project Member, I want to list issue log items, so that I can manage them. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US42	As a Project Member, I want to update issue log items, so that I can keep the issue log up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US43	As a Project Member, I want to delete issue log items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US44	As a Project Member, I want to create issue log items, so that I can organize the project issues. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have

US45	As a Project Member, I want to list issue log items, so that I can manage them. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US46	As a Project Member, I want to update issue log items, so that I can keep the issue log up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US47	As a Project Member, I want to delete issue log items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US48	As a Project Member, I want to create lesson learned items, so that I can organize experiences gained for future projects. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US49	As a Project Member, I want to list lesson learned items, so that I can manage them. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US50	As a Project Member, I want to update lesson learned items, so that I can keep the lessons learned up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US51	As a Project Member, I want to delete lesson learned items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US52	As a Project Member, I want to create change request items, so that I can organize the project modifications. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US53	As a Project Member, I want to list change request items, so that I can manage them. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US54	As a Project Member, I want to update change request items, so that I can keep the change requests up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US55	As a Project Member, I want to delete change request items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US56	As a Project Member, I want to list a log of change request status, so that I can see their status.	Implemented	Must Have
US57	As a Project Member, I want to create the project closure report, so that I can summarize the project results. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US58	As a Project Member, I want to update the project closure report, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US59	As a Project Member, I want to create the final report, so that I can officially end the project. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have

US60	As a Project Member, I want to update the final report, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (integration)	Implemented	Must Have
US61	As a Project Member, I want to create the requirements management plan, so that I can define how requirements will be managed. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US62	As a Project Member, I want to update the requirements management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US63	As a Project Member, I want to create the scope management plan, so that I can define how the scope will be managed. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US64	As a Project Member, I want to update the scope management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US65	As a Project Member, I want to create requirements registration items, so that I can organize the project requirements. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US66	As a Project Member, I want to list the requirements registration items, so that I can managem them. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US67	As a Project Member, I want to update the requirements registration items, so that I can keep the items up-to-date. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US68	As a Project Member, I want to delete the requirements registration items, so that I can remove unecessary data. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US69	As a Project Member, I want to create the project scope statement, so that I can define the project boundaries. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US70	As a Project Member, I want to update the project scope statement, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US71	As a Project Member, I want to view the Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) as I register activities, so that I don't need external tools for my project structure.	Not Implemented	Must Have
US72	As a Project Member, I want to create the schedule management plan, so that I can define how the schedule will be managed. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have
US73	As a Project Member, I want to update the schedule management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (scope)	Implemented	Must Have

US74	As a Project Member, I want to create activities, so that I can organize what needs to be done. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US75	As a Project Member, I want to list activities, so that I can see what needs to be done. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US76	As a Project Member, I want to update activities, so that I keep my activities up-to-date as changes are made. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US77	As a Project Member, I want to delete activities, so that I can discard activities that no long will be done. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US78	As a Project Member, I want to view indexes of earn value management as cost estimates are registered, so that I can see the project progress. (schedule)	Not Implemented	Must Have
US79	As a Project Member, I want to create a logical sequence between activities, so that I can register the dependency between them. (schedule)	Not Implemented	Must Have
US80	As a Project Member, I want to list schedule network diagram items, so that I can navigate between them. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US81	As a Project Member, I want to view that logical sequence between activities as a flow, so that I can see what are the critical tasks. (schedule)	Proposed	Must Have
US82	As a Project Member, I want to update schedule network diagram items, so that I can keep the logical sequence up-to-date. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US83	As a Project Member, I want to delete schedule network diagram items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US84	As a Project Member, I want to create resource requirements, so that I can register my resources. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US85	As a Project Member, I want to list resource requirements, so that I can manage my resources. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US86	As a Project Member, I want to update resource requirements, so that I can keep my resources up-to-date. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US87	As a Project Member, I want to delete resource requirements, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have

US88	As a Project Member, I want to create duration estimates of activities, so that I can organize the schedule of activities. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US89	As a Project Member, I want to list duration estimates of activities, so that I can manage the schedule of activities. (schedule)	Implemented	Must Have
US90	As a Project Member, I want to update duration estimates of activities, so that I can keep the schedule of activities up-to-date. (schedule)	Not Implemented	Must Have
US91	As a Project Member, I want to delete duration estimates of activities, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (schedule)	Not Implemented	Must Have
US92	As a Project Member, I want to create the cost management plan, so that I can define how the cost will be managed. (cost)	Implemented	Must Have
US93	As a Project Member, I want to update the cost management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (cost)	Implemented	Must Have
US94	As a Project Member, I want to create the cost estimates items, so that I can organize the cost of tasks. (cost)	Implemented	Must Have
US95	As a Project Member, I want to list the cost estimates plan items, so that I can manage them. (cost)	Implemented	Must Have
US96	As a Project Member, I want to update the cost estimates items, so that I can keep the items up-to-date. (cost)	Implemented	Must Have
US97	As a Project Member, I want to create the quality management plan, so that I can define how the quality will be managed. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US98	As a Project Member, I want to update the quality management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US99	As a Project Member, I want to create product quality checklist items, so that I can organize the acceptancy of our project quality aspects. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US100	As a Project Member, I want to product quality checklist items, so that I can manage them. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US101	As a Project Member, I want to updateproduct quality checklist items, so that I can keep the schedule of activities up-to-date. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have

US102	As a Project Member, I want to delete product quality checklist items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US103	As a Project Member, I want to create quality reports, so that I can the quality control. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US104	As a Project Member, I want to list duration quality reports, so that I can manage them. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US105	As a Project Member, I want to update quality reports, so that I can keep the items up-to-date. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US106	As a Project Member, I want to delete quality reports, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (quality)	Implemented	Must Have
US107	As a Project Member, I want to create the resources management plan, so that I can define how the resources will be managed. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US108	As a Project Member, I want to update the resources plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US109	As a Project Member, I want to create resource breakdown structures, so that I can register project resource structures. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US110	As a Project Member, I want to list resource breakdown structures, so that I can manage them. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US111	As a Project Member, I want to delete resource breakdown structures, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US112	As a Project Member, I want to create team performance assessments, so that I can organize the team member strengths. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US113	As a Project Member, I want to list team performance assessments, so that I can manage them. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US114	As a Project Member, I want to update team performance assessments, so that I can keep the team performance assessments up-to-date. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have
US115	As a Project Member, I want to delete team performance assessments, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (resource)	Implemented	Must Have

US116	As a Project Member, I want to create communication management plan items, so that I can define how the communication will be managed. (communication)	Implemented	Must Have
US117	As a Project Member, I want to list communication management plan items, so that I can manage them. (communication)	Implemented	Must Have
US118	As a Project Member, I want to update communication management plan items, so that I can keep them up-to-date. (communication)	Implemented	Must Have
US119	As a Project Member, I want to delete communication management plan items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (communication)	Implemented	Must Have
US120	As a Project Member, I want to create the risk management plan, so that I can define how the risk will be managed. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US121	As a Project Member, I want to update the risk management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US122	As a Project Member, I want to register risk, so that I can organize potential risks and responses for them. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US123	As a Project Member, I want to list the risks, so that I can manage them. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US124	As a Project Member, I want to update a risk, so that I can keep them up-to-date. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US125	As a Project Member, I want to delete a risk, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US126	As a Project Member, I want to create general project risk checklist items, so that I can organize the impact and probability of risks. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US127	As a Project Member, I want to list general project risk checklist items, so that I can manage them. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US128	As a Project Member, I want to update general project risk checklist items, so that I can keep them up-to-date. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have
US129	As a Project Member, I want to delete general project risk checklist items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (risk)	Implemented	Must Have

US130	As a Project Member, I want to create the procurement management plan, so that I can define how the procurements will be managed. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US131	As a Project Member, I want to update the procurement management plan, so that I can keep the document up-to-date. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US132	As a Project Member, I want to create procurement statements of work, so that I can procurements details. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US133	As a Project Member, I want to list procurement statements of work, so that I can manage them. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US134	As a Project Member, I want to update procurement statements of work, so that I can keep them up-to-date. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US135	As a Project Member, I want to delete procurement, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US136	As a Project Member, I want to create closed procurement documentation items, so that I can the closing of procurements. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US137	As a Project Member, I want to list closed procurement documentation items, so that I can manage them. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US138	As a Project Member, I want to update closed procurement documentation items, so that I can keep them up-to-date. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US139	As a Project Member, I want to delete closed procurement documentation items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (procurement)	Implemented	Must Have
US140	As a Project Member, I want to register stakeholder, so that I can organize the project stakeholders. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have
US141	As a Project Member, I want to list stakeholder, so that I can manage them. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have
US142	As a Project Member, I want to update stakeholder items, so that I can keep them of activities up-to-date. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have

US143	As a Project Member, I want to delete stakeholders, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have
US144	As a Project Member, I want to create stakeholder engagement plan items, so that I can organize stakeholder engagement plan items. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have
US145	As a Project Member, I want to list stakeholder engagement plan items, so that I can manage them. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have
US146	As a Project Member, I want to update stakeholder engagement plan items, so that I can keep them up-to-date. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Must Have
US147	As a Project Member, I want to delete stakeholder engagement plan items, so that I can remove unnecessary data. (stakeholder)	Implemented	Should Have
US148	As a Project Member, I want to create stakeholder calendar items, so that I can define when the stakeholders will be available.	Implemented	Should Have
US149	As a Project Member, I want to list stakeholder calendar items, so that I can manage the stakeholders' availability.	Implemented	Should Have
US150	As a Project Member, I want to update stakeholder calendar items, so that I can keep the stakeholders' availability up-to-date.	Implemented	Should Have
US151	As a Project Member, I want to delete stakeholder calendar items, so that I remove those who left the project.	Implemented	Should Have
US152	As a Professor, I want to evaluate, numerically (Likert Scale), the documents or processes created by the students, so that I can give feedback to my students.	Not Implemented	Should Have
US153	As a Student, I want to export the project data in an integrated way to Latex source-code (Overleaf), so that it facilitates the process of submitting activity reports to the professors at each milestone.	In Progress	Should Have
US154	As a Professor, I want to comment on each of the components of the documents created by the students (similarly, the students can view the comments and respond to them), so that I can give feedback to my students about the content of each component of project artifacts.	In Progress	Must Have

US155	As a Professor, I want to configure the formative assessments planned in the project, so that I can create a schedule for delivering assignments to students.	Not Implemented	Should Have
US156	As a Student, I want to I want to periodically report their activities (Logbook), allowing the inclusion of external files as evidence, so that I I can report my activities and evidence of performed tasks.	Not Implemented	Should Have
US157	As a Student, I want to earn points, badges, or other rewards and to compete or collaborate with peers in gamified challenges, so that I I can motivate and track my progress in learning journey and enhance my social interaction and teamwork skills.	Proposed	Should Have